

Challenges Associated with the Security of Records in Federal University Otuoke Library

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigated the challenges associated with the security of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library. Four research questions guided this study.

Methodology: The study employed a descriptive survey approach. The population included 28 library staff members. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire with 4-point Likert scales. Out of these, 25 library staff at Federal University Otuoke participated via census sampling. The collected data were analysed using percentages and means.

Findings: The findings show that inadequate power supply, virus attacks, technological obsolescence, inadequate infrastructure, security breaches, inadequate funding, and the absence of a Records Management Policy are among the challenges associated with the security of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library.

Conclusion: The study concludes that library management should take adequate measures to acquire solar energy as an alternative to the power supply.

Study implications: The Federal University Otuoke should focus on managing electronic records. Additionally, library staff should be periodically sponsored to attend training on record management.

Study Type: Research Paper

Keywords: Records security, Challenges, University Library, Nigeria.

Introduction

University libraries are vital components of the academic environment, serving as custodians of recorded knowledge, including books, journals, digital resources, and administrative records. According to Sadiq (2020), university libraries are systems established, administered, and funded by a university to meet the information, research, and curriculum needs of its students, faculty, and staff. Some of the responsibilities of university libraries include preserving knowledge, providing access to and retrieving information resources, supporting teaching, learning, research, and community development, and ensuring that records are adequately secure to support services. Chukwuji and Umeji (2020) state that University libraries build networks/consortia to ensure the university community has access to almost every available and relevant knowledge/information needed to advance and create knowledge.

The term "record" is defined by Solis (2020) as a document created, received, and maintained. John and Lawrence (2023) also define records as an organisation's memory—the things an organisation creates, processes, sends, uses, saves, finds, keeps, and eventually discards. In like manner, Allison (2021) defines records as the memory of an organisation. They are organisational assets that are created, processed, transmitted, used, stored, retrieved, retained, and eventually destroyed. University libraries manage large volumes of records due to their multifaceted role within the university community. According to Akinola (2020), university libraries are intellectual banks that provide avenues for students and faculty to research and improve their knowledge. Also, Ibeh and Ezebasili (2024) state that libraries are large repositories of important records, and librarians ensure that these records are well-maintained so that they remain accurate, accessible, and useful. Enakrire (2020) states that records fulfil the functions of activities in the contemporary workplace, irrespective of the organisation. Muthoni (2018) affirms that any organisation's success depends on effective records management practices that ensure the right records are made available when needed for effective operation.

Records security in university libraries is essential for maintaining the trust and confidence of library users and the academic community. It also supports the library's mission to provide high-quality information services and resources. Library collections constitute the bedrock of services provided to the community and are important assets of the library. Akpobasah and Ogunbadejo (2022) asserted that securing and protecting collections can help libraries provide effective services to meet the information needs of the academic community.

Statement of Problem

Federal University Otuoke was established in 2012. The Federal University Otuoke Library is an integrated network of the Central Library comprising three reading halls, a Scholars Research Den, the Bruce Powell e-Library, Faculty Libraries, and the School of Graduate Library. The university library has a staff strength of 64. This comprised 12 professional staff, 8 para-professional staff, and 44 supporting staff (administrative staff inclusive). Facilities in the library include 1,504 seats, internet access, 105 computers for users, and 5 faculty and departmental libraries. The library learning and research resources comprise twenty-one thousand and thirty-six (21,036) volumes of books, two thousand two hundred and fifty journal titles, and 66 E-resources. As the custodian of academic, research, and administrative records, the university library has faced several challenges in securing them. Challenges such as theft, mutilation, environmental damage, cyber threats, unauthorised access, and financial issues related to technological advancement have hindered the library's ability to establish an adequate security system. All these threats have a severe effect on the university's community. Against this backdrop, the researchers aim to investigate the challenges associated with the security of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library.

Research Questions

The following questions guided this study

1. What are the types of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library
2. What are the various ways records have supported the Federal University Otuoke Library
3. What are the challenges in securing Federal University Otuoke Library records?
4. What is the best security measure in managing library records?

Literature Review

Libraries, as repositories of knowledge, acquire, distribute, use, maintain, conserve and above all, secure records to render effective services. One major goal of a university library is to meet user satisfaction. Akpan and Akpan (2018) noted that the university library is the principal instrument of the university in the conservation of recorded knowledge. Proper fulfilment of this role provides a sound basis for transmitting and advancing knowledge. To achieve its aims, university libraries acquire materials ranging from books to non-book formats, including digital resources such as electronic books, e-journals, and online databases. Sambo, et al. (2014) studies revealed that types of records commonly stored in the university libraries includes, books and journals acquired, periodical appraisal of records, staff files, library holdings, minute of meeting, receipts of money received, library equipment, actual budget allocation, releases and retiring/shipment receipts and purchase order, sitting capacity of the library, files and reports/budget request. Nwachukwu, Abdulsalami, and Lucky (2014) on the availability, accessibility and use of information resources and services among information seekers of Lafia Public Library in Nasarawa State, described library records as books, serials and journal publications, and electronic source documents (non-print, e.g. audio-visual) in the library. Endouware and Okwu's (2023) study on librarians' perceptions of the security of library resources in university libraries in Bayelsa state, Nigeria revealed Textbooks, Journals, Magazines, Newspapers, Reference materials, Cartographic materials, Digital/Electronic materials, Internet facilities, Students' projects, and online public access catalogues as the major available records in university libraries in Bayelsa State. According to Porter-Roth (2006), organisations create, receive, and manage records in large volumes and handle them in various formats, such as e-mail, short messages, faxes, and so forth.

Security of records in university libraries is essential for maintaining the trust and confidence of library users and the academic community. It also supports the library's mission to provide high-quality information services and resources. Records are necessary components of organisations. Touray (2021) states that records enhance accountability, business continuity, compliance and efficiency. The need for record security is indisputable. Agu et al. (2022) studied records management and organisational performance. The study revealed that adequate security of organisational records enables proper identification and location of records, easy user access, and accountability among staff. Otodo and Alegbeleye (2021) posited that records are barometers for measuring the performance of an organisation, which means that without records, no organisation can function. Bakare, Owolabi and Yusuf (2019) assessed records management systems at the Institute of Continuing Education, Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study revealed that effective records management was beneficial to the smooth running of the Institute, as it enabled timely attention to institutional and student demands. Specifically, the findings indicate that proper records management sustains corporate and institutional memory, facilitates rapid decision-making, and helps meet students' demands.

Studies have identified the challenges of securing records as a lack of policies and guidelines, rapid technological change, inadequate facilities, and incompetent record personnel. Egwunyenga (2009) confirmed that African record keepers lack the basic skills and competencies required to manage records and archives in the public sector. There is a serious problem of technophobia in most offices in Africa, especially among older employees. Due to inadequate information technology skills, many traditional librarians, records managers, and archivists are conservative and have a phobia of computers. This may be due to generational gaps between new and older professionals, which led analogue information managers to perceive computers as undermining their status as experts. Also, Egwunyenga (2009) noted that proper record-keeping by library managers is constrained by insufficient librarian skills, lack of infrastructure, storage issues, poor supervision, and inadequate records management programmes in Nigerian Universities. Thus, the management of school records is a matter of great concern to stakeholders in education. Ojedokun (2008) noted that older librarians are reluctant to abandon

established practices in favour of new ones. The successful application of information-handling technologies to electronic records management in developing countries requires the competence to address staff and personal resistance. Records in Nigerian universities are characterised by unprofessional destruction, improper arrangement and description, the absence of a proper disaster-prevention plan, and a general lack of guidelines for managing the records lifecycle (Abdulrazaq, 2015). Brendan (2013) found that there are no functional policies in place to manage records, resulting in their repeated loss due to inefficient filing systems at universities.

The security of library records is vital to its operations. For the library to meet its goals and objectives, security measures must be adopted to safeguard records. Akpobasah and Ogunbadejo (2022) findings reveal that the security measure in the library includes the use of ownership stamps on textbooks, entrance door security measures and electronic gadgets such as alarm systems, closed-circuit television (CCTV), 3M exit detection; Biometrics; Electronic Eye Detection; Electronic Recording; Network and Server Security Systems; Smart Card; Antivirus Software; RFID Book Drop System; RFID Transponder and Reader system; and Moisture and Glass Breaker System respectively. This indicates that universities employ both traditional and 21st-century security measures to safeguard their records against theft and mutilation. The study recommends the use of advanced technologies, such as touch detectors and barcodes, to enhance the security of library records. Echem and Okwu's (2023) study on library security and sustainable service delivery in Donald Ekong Library, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, indicated the use of smart card access control, CCTV, fire extinguisher, installation of window burglary, door intrusion alarm, panic alarm, perimeter alarm system and RFID as types of security measures adopted. The study recommended establishing a maintenance culture to sustain the existing security system in the library.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised twenty-eight (28) library staff. This includes librarians, para-professional librarians and supporting staff (administrative staff) in the Federal University Otuoke Library. A sample of 28 library staff members, comprising the entire population, was used for the study. This study adopted a census sampling method. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data, with 4-point Likert scales. Twenty-five (25) out of twenty-eight (28) distributed copies of the questionnaire were filled, returned and used for analysis. Data collected from the respondents were analysed using percentages and means. A criterion mean score of 2.5 or above is accepted, and a score below 2.5 is rejected. The result of the study is presented below.

Analysis of Demography

Respondent's Demographic Information

Table 1. Professional status

Professional Status		
Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Librarians	18	72
Para-professional Librarian	4	16
Administrative Staff	3	12
Total	25	100

Table 1 shows that 18 (72%) of the responses, representing the majority of respondents, are from Librarians, followed by Para-professional librarians (4 [16%]), and 3 (12%) are administrative staff of the Federal University Otuoke Library. This implied that the majority of the library staff are librarians.

Table 2. Academic qualifications of the respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PhD	7	28
MLIS/MSc	6	24
BLIS/	5	20
BSc	3	12
HND	3	12
OND	1	4
Total	25	100

Table 2. shows that majority of the respondents 7(28%) were Ph.D. holders, 6(24%) were MLIS holders, 5(20%) BLIS holders, 3(12%) BSc holders, 3(12%) HND holders, and 1(4%) OND holders. This implies that the majority of respondents under study were PhD holders.

Table 3. Years of experience

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18– 30 Years	11	44
31 years and above	14	56
Total	25	100

Table 3 shows that 11(44%) of the respondents were between 18 to 30 years old, and 14(56%) are within the age of 31 years and above. This means that the majority of the library staff are 31 years and above.

Table 4. Gender of the respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	14	58
Female	11	44
Total		100

Table 4. revealed that 14(58%) of the respondents are male while 11(44%) are female. This means that the majority of the library staff were male.

Research Question 1: Types of Records in the Federal University Otuoke Library

Table 5. Responses to Research Question 1

S/No	Types of Library Records	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1	Books (textbooks, reference books, periodicals, scholarly journals, etc)	12	13	-	-	3.48
2	Digital Resources (E-books, online databases, E-journals, etc.)	10	13	2	-	3.32
3	Archival materials	9	11	4	1	3.12

4	Multimedia collection	8	12	3	2	3.04
5	Special collection	9	13	2	1	3.20
6	Research data	10	11	3	1	3.20
7	Statistical records (registered users, books acquired, books catalogued, books charged and discharged, etc)	7	9	8	1	2.88
8	Administrative records (personnel records, inventory records, queries, promotions, leaves, appraisals, etc)	11	12	1	1	3.32
						3.20

Table 5 revealed the types of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library. All the items in Table 2 have mean values above the criterion mean of 2.5. Furthermore, the grand mean score of 3.32 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.5. This indicates that the Federal University Otuoke Library maintains a diverse range of records. Most notable among the types of record available in their library are Books (textbooks, reference books, periodicals, scholarly journals), and Digital Resources (E-books, online databases, E-journals), with mean values of 3.48 and 3.32, respectively.

Research Question 2: How does the security of records support the Federal University Otuoke Library

Table 6. Responses to Research Question 2

S/NO	Security Support	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1	It sustains corporate and institutional memory.	8	13	3	1	3.12
2	It guides against data breaches and unauthorised disclosure.	9	11	3	2	3.28
3	It supports accurate and complete records.	11	12	1	1	3.32
4	It serves as a backbone for the success of the library.	12	10	2	1	3.32
5	Easy access to records helps to improve customer service.	13	10	1	1	3.40
6	It enables proper identification and location of records.	9	11	4	1	3.12
7	It aids the library in planning and decision-making.	10	11	2	2	3.32
8	It enhances accountability.	8	13	3	1	3.12
						3.25

Table 6 revealed how the security of records supports the Federal University Otuoke Library. All the listed items in Table 3 have mean values above the criterion mean of 2.5. Furthermore, the grand mean (3.25) is greater than the criterion mean. This demonstrates that the security of records effectively supports the Federal University Otuoke Library. Most notable among others on how the security of records supports the Federal University Otuoke Library are easy access to records, which improves customer service, knowledge upgrade, and serves as a backbone for the success of the library, with mean values of 3.40 and 3.32, respectively

Research Question 3: challenges in securing Federal University Otuoke Library records**Table 7. Responses to Research Question 3**

S/NO	Challenges in Securing Library Records	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1	Inadequate Funding.	6	16	1	2	3.04
2	Absence of Records Management Policy.	7	8	6	4	2.72
3	Obsolescence of Technology	11	12	1	1	3.32
4	Inadequate power supply	13	10	1	1	3.40
5	Virus attack	11	13	1	-	3.40
6	Security breaches	10	13	2	-	3.24
7	Inadequate infrastructure	9	15	1		3.32
						3.21

Table 7 presents the respondents' response rates regarding challenges in securing Federal University Otuoke Library records. All the items listed in Table 4 have mean values above the criterion mean of 2.5; furthermore, the grand mean (3.21) is greater than the criterion mean (2.5). This indicates that all items in Table 7 pose challenges to securing Federal University Otuoke Library records. Most challenges, among others, include Inadequate power supply, virus attacks, technology obsolescence, and inadequate infrastructure, with mean values of 3.4 and 3.3, respectively.

Research Question 4: Best security measure in the management of library records.**Table 8. Responses to Research Question 3**

S/NO	security measures in the management of library records.	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1	There should be an adequate budget in place to be able to fund all the needs of record security	12	13	-	1	2.48
2	Records policy should be developed	8	9	5	3	2.88
3	Technological gadgets should be updated regularly	12	11	2	-	3.40
4	Provision should be made for an alternative power supply	10	12	3	-	3.28
5	Provision should be made for anti-virus	11	14	-	-	3.44
6	Access control should be strengthened by using encryption and password	9	10	3	3	3.00
7	There should be in place fire-resistant equipment to fight against fire outbreaks	13	12	-	-	3.52
8	There should be a backup to support the records	8	17	-	-	3.32
						3.17

Table 8 presents the most effective security measures for managing library records. All listed items in Table 5 have mean values that are above the criterion mean of 2.5; moreover, the grand mean (3.25) is greater than the criterion mean (2.5), and this shows that all the items in the table are among the best security measures in the management of library records. Notable among the best security measures in

managing library records are fire-resistant equipment to combat fire outbreaks and antivirus protection, with mean values of 3.52 and 3.44, respectively.

Discussion of findings

Types of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library

The study revealed that types of records in the Federal University Otuoke Library includes, books (textbooks, reference books, periodicals, scholarly journals), Digital Resources (E-books, online databases, E-journals), archival materials, Multimedia collection, special collection, research data, Statistical records (registered users, books acquired, books catalogued, books charged and discharged) and Administrative records (personnel records, inventory records, queries, promotions, leaves, appraiser. This is consistent with the findings of Sambo et al. (2014), who reported that records commonly stored in university libraries include books and journals acquired, periodical/appraisal/promotion/conference records, staff files, library holdings, meeting minutes, and receipts.

How the security of records supports the Federal University Otuoke Library

According to the respondents, how record security supports the Federal University Otuoke Library includes easy access to records, which improves customer service, knowledge upgrading, and record security, serving as the backbone of the library. This is therefore in conformity with the findings of Agu et al. (2022), whose studies revealed that adequate safety of organisational records enables proper identification and location of records, easy access to records by users and accountability among staff.

Challenges in securing Federal University Otuoke Library records

The challenges in securing Federal University Otuoke Library records, as indicated by the responses, include inadequate power supply, virus attacks, technological obsolescence, inadequate infrastructure, security breaches, insufficient funding, and the absence of a records management policy. This is consistent with the findings of Egwunyenga (2009), who noted that proper record-keeping by library managers is constrained by insufficient librarian skills, inadequate infrastructure, storage problems, poor supervision, and weak records management programmes in Nigerian Universities.

Best security measure in the management of library records

The best security measure in the management of library records was discovered through the response of the respondents, to include: There should be in place fire-resistant equipment to fight against fire outbreaks, provision should be made for anti-virus, there should be backup to support the records, and provision should be made for alternative power supply. This is therefore in conformity with the findings of Akpobasah and Ogunbadejo (2022) whose studies reveal that the security measure in the library includes the use of ownership stamps on textbooks, entrance door security measures and electronic gadgets such as alarm systems, closed-circuit television (CCTV), 3M exit detection; Biometrics; Electronic Eye Detection; Electronic Recording; Network and Server Security Systems; Smart Card; Antivirus Software.

Conclusion

Records are the life wire of every organisation. Organisations' success and failure depend greatly on their records. The security of records in the library is a vital key to its operations. For the library to meet its goals and objectives, security measures must be implemented to safeguard records. This study confirmed that inadequate power supply, virus attack, obsolescence of technology, inadequate infrastructure, security breaches, inadequate funding and absence of records Management Policy are

among the challenges associated with the security of records in Federal University Otuoke Library. The researchers recommended that library management should take adequate measures to acquire solar energy as an alternative to the power supply. Federal University Otuoke should pay attention to electronic records. Also, Library staff should be sponsored at intervals to attend training on record management. This will keep them abreast of trends in record management.

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